

The following points emerge on comparing the above dyes (I and II) with phenolphthalein :

Titration of iodide ions against silver ions : With 0.1*N* KI solution the adsorption indicators I, II and phenolphthalein show the coagulation of the slightly coloured (orange or pinkish or violet shaded-yellow) ppt. With 0.02*N* solutions the coagulated ppt. is more pronounced in adsorbility. With 0.01*N*-0.005*N* solutions dye I seems to have adsorbed better than II and phenolphthalein. With 0.0025*N* solutions I shows good orange ppt, II and phenolphthalein shows good pink ppt. The dyes I, II, and phenolphthalein can also be used for 0.00125*N* solution but coagulation takes place after shaking the solution well at the end point.

Conclusion

3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I) is in some respects better than phenolphthalein as it can be used in neutral (0.1-0.00125*N* solutions) and as well as in alkaline (0.1-0.01*N* solutions) conditions; with solutions 0.01-0.005*N* it seems to have adsorbed better. Dyes III-V, can only be used for higher concentration of the solutions (0.1-0.05*N*). Dyes VI and VII are unsuitable as adsorption indicators.

References

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Studies on Adsorption Indicators. Part II. Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides as Adsorption Indicators in Argentometric Titrations of Chloride Ions

E. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Ewing Christian College, Allahabad

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MEHROTRA¹ has reported the use of phenolphthalein (in slightly alkaline condition) as adsorption indicator for the titration of chloride ions.

In the present communication the studies have been extended to seven new similar and unsymmetrical phthalides* (Mono- and bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides). Thus, 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide

(I), 3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II), 3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III), 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV), 3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2 : 3-naphthalide (V), β -1-naphthyl-phenolsuccinein (VI), and β -2-naphthyl-phenolsuccinein (VII) have been studied for their utility as adsorption indicators in the argentometric titrations of chloride ions.

Experimental

Materials used : AgNO₃ and NaCl used were A.R. (BDH) grade reagents.

Indicator solution, Preparation of the dyes, and Procedure see².

Results and Discussion

The dye (I) red in colour, has absorption maxima of 5300 Å (both in neutral and alkaline condition)³. In the neutral medium it can be easily used as an indicator for solutions ranging in dilution from 0.1-0.005*N* but in slightly alkaline condition it can only be used in solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. II, like phenolphthalein and I can be easily used for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*. For solutions 0.004-0.0025*N*, I, II, and phenolphthalein can be used if the solutions are vigorously shaken even after the end point is reached. III can be used for solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. IV and V can be used for 0.1*N* dilution only. VI and VII are unsuitable.

Detailed studies of dyes I and II as adsorption indicators are shown in the Table.

The adsorbility and colour changes of the dyes (I-V) have been compared with phenolphthalein as follows :

3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I) : Titrations easily possible in neutral medium for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*; in alkaline condition for solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. Suspension (white with orange tinge) → pink; orange-pink; and orange ppt.

3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) : Titrations easily possible for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*. Suspension (pinkish white or violet soln.) → violet ppt.

3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III) : Titrations possible for 0.1-0.02*N* solutions. Suspension (white with violet tinge) → light violet ppt.

3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) : Titration possible for 0.1*N* solution only. Suspension (orange shaded-white) → violet-ash ppt.

3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2 : 3-naphthalide (V) : Titration possible for 0.1*N* solution. Suspension (white with pink tinge) → ash coloured ppt.

Conclusion

The following points emerge on comparing the above dyes (I and II) with phenolphthalein :

*Part I, see *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 948.

NOTES

TABLE—DYES I (USED IN NEUTRAL MEDIUM) AND II (USED IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE CONDITION) AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS. VOLUME OF NaCl TAKEN FOR TITRATION : 10 ml

Dye	Concn. of NaCl	Vol. and concn. of AgNO ₃	Drops of indicator	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1N	10.00 ml 0.1N	10	orange-yellow tinged white suspn. → pink ppt.	complete coagulation and clear supernatant liquid at the end point
I	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	8	orange tinged white soln. → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.005N	10.00 ml 0.005N	4	light orange-yellow turbidity → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.004N	10.02 ml 0.004N	4	orange tinged turbid → orange ppt.	coagulation takes place after vigorous shaking and standing.
II	0.1N	10.00 ml 0.1N	10	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation starts 6 drops before the end point but complete coagulation takes place at the end point leaving violet tinged supernatant liquid.
II	0.02N	10.00 ml 0.2N	8	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation at the end point; supernatant liquid almost clear.
II	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	6	pink tinged white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation at the end point; supernatant liquid faint violet-pink.
II	0.005N	10.00 ml 0.005N	3	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	same as above.
II	0.004N	10.02 ml 0.004N	3	same as above.	same as above but coagulation requires vigorous shaking.
II	0.0025N	10.02 ml 0.0025N	3	same as above.	same as above.

That phenolphthalein certainly shows good adsorption properties in slightly alkaline condition, and that dye II is as good as phenolphthalein.

That dye I has the advantage over phenolphthalein and Dye II, that it can be used in neutral as well as in alkaline condition, the former condition being the better.

That dyes III-V, can only be used for solutions of higher concentration; and dyes VI and VII are unsuitable as adsorption indicators.

References

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Preparation and Characterisation of α -Chloro- β -(3:4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid

S. P. DHOUBHADEL

Department of Chemistry, Tribhuvan University, Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

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α -HALO- β -PHENYL substituted acrylic acids are usually obtained by the methods of Sudborough and Thompson¹ and Sudborough and James². The isolation and characterisation of methyl- $[\alpha$ -chloro-

β -3:4-methylenedioxyphenyl]-acrylate (II) was reported by the author³. In the present communication the preparation of the acid (I) is reported. Thus α -halo- β -phenyl substituted acids are now accessible by a new route.

Darzens glycidic ester condensation of piperonal with methyl chloroacetate in presence of methanolic sodium methoxide afforded the compound (II) which was hydrolysed to give its sodium salt (III).

- (I), R = H
 (II), R = CH₃
 (III), R = Na.

The sodium salt was smoothly converted to the acid (I) by acidification. The new compound (I) was characterised by analytical and spectroscopic methods.

The compound responded to Beilstein test for chlorine. The vinylic chlorine resisted hydrolysis. The mass spectrum of the compound, (C₁₀H₇O₄Cl) displayed the molecular ion at m/e 226 and the peak at m/e 228 was approximately one-third of the molecular ion peak. The nmr spectrum showed the absence of the methyl proton signals when compared with that of the ester. The carboxylic proton was